

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No8
2025

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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 68 sahifa,
1-avgust, 2025-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

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Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS OF ESP LEARNERS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Abstract: This paper explores the effectiveness of integrating digital tools into English classes within the ESP (English for Specific Purposes) domain and investigates the impact of digitalization through pedagogical theories. Furthermore, it highlights the drawbacks of traditional teaching methods and the advantages of digitalized classes using several methodological approaches.

Key words: Development, pedagogy, digital tools, English classes, traditional, technologies, approaches, methods, teachers, students, research, communication, role play, interaction, game-based learning, platforms, applications.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ESP (kasbiy maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili) sohasida ingliz tili darslariga raqamli vositalarni integratsiya qilishning samaradorligi yoritilgan, shuningdek, raqamlashtirishning ta'limiy nazariyalar asosidagi ta'siri o'rganilgan. Maqolada, shuningdek, an'anaviy o'qitish uslublarining kamchiliklari va raqamlashtirilgan darslarning afzalliklari turli yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Rivojlanish, pedagogika, raqamli vositalar, ingliz tili darslari, an'anaviy, texnologiyalar, yondashuvlar, usullar, o'qituvchilar, talabalar, tadqiqot, muloqot, rolli o'yin, o'zaro ta'sir, o'yin asosidagi o'qitish, platformalar, ilovalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается эффективность интеграции цифровых инструментов в преподавание английского языка в сфере ESP (английский язык для специальных целей), а также исследуется влияние цифровизации на основе педагогических теорий. Кроме того, анализируются недостатки традиционных методов обучения и преимущества цифровых занятий с позиции различных методологических подходов.

Ключевые слова: Развитие, педагогика, цифровые инструменты, уроки английского языка, традиционные методы, технологии, подходы, методы, учителя, студенты, исследование, общение, ролевая игра, взаимодействие, игровое обучение, платформы, приложения.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized society, the ability to speak English fluently, naturally, and confidently is becoming increasingly important for professionals across all fields. Students in non-philological disciplines are encountering a growing need to communicate in English in international relations, academic research, and professional contexts. However, outdated traditional methods of language instruction often hinder the achievement of such goals. These methods fail to effectively engage learners in active communication and are insufficient in addressing pedagogical barriers to speaking. Therefore, it has become essential to develop oral speech skills through the use of digital technologies, which calls for a reassessment of theoretical foundations. "Digital tools possess the potential to fundamentally reshape the process of teaching speaking skills by creating interactive and multimodal conditions, thereby increasing learner engagement and autonomy" (Godwin-Jones, 2018).

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted global education systems. During the ensuing shift to distance and, in many cases, blended learning formats, language instructors around the world observed a decline in the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods. Many interactive instructional techniques such as games, debates, case studies, and projects lost their vitality, emotional intensity, and pedagogical effectiveness. Technical limitations of digital platforms like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Skype reduced the educational and developmental impact of these methods. These challenges particularly affected non-philological students, hindering the development of key foreign language competencies, including: the ability to

produce spontaneous speech, quick and context-appropriate verbal responses, simulation of professional conversations, interpersonal collaboration, team management skills. At the same time, the global spread of the coronavirus increased learners' motivation and capacity to study foreign languages independently. As a result, there emerged a critical need to investigate pedagogical technologies, strategies, methodologies, and learning tools that support communicative competence and are tailored to specific professional needs—tools that can be used individually or collaboratively across various platforms and applications.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Due to these emergency conditions, universities worldwide were compelled to shift from traditional face-to-face instruction to remote education, requiring the development of new, modern approaches to English language teaching. It soon became evident that relying solely on traditional methods and classroom-based communication made mastering spoken English a tedious and difficult process. Simply replacing the classroom with platforms like Zoom, Teams, Skype, or Moodle offered only limited interaction. Today, however, digital technologies present exciting and innovative opportunities for language learning. Students can engage with virtual realities, interact through various applications on tablets, and learn through high-definition simulations of real-world environments. These technologies have become an inseparable part of everyday life.

In this context, the use of digital tools in teaching English—particularly through authentic materials drawn from real-life situations—is gaining popularity, especially in courses for non-philological learners. Just as in other subjects, the integration of digital technologies in teaching English to non-language majors carries several pedagogical and psychological considerations. In fact, one of the key paradigms of 21st-century language education is the effective use of digital learning technologies within the teaching process. This is particularly true when developing and enhancing speaking skills among non-philological students, where interaction-based environments, multimedia tools, virtual platforms, and artificial intelligence-powered applications are proving increasingly valuable. The integration of digital technologies into English language instruction should be informed by pedagogical theories. Careful attention must be given to the planning and implementation of instructional goals and tasks. “Engaging non-language learners in real-life communicative situations, strengthening their pedagogical preparedness, and encouraging verbal activity are among the strongest advantages of digital technologies” (Trofimova, E.V., 2020).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In modern education, the focus has shifted toward the development of competencies—not merely teaching knowledge or content, but enabling students to integrate knowledge, skills, and attitudes in a meaningful and applied way. The improvement of oral communication skills through digital technologies is fully aligned with this competency-based approach. Within this framework, language is not viewed merely as the acquisition of grammar or vocabulary, but as the ability to use language effectively in real-life professional and social contexts. “The ultimate goal of language learning is to develop the learner’s communicative competence—that is, the ability to use the target language meaningfully and purposefully in real-life situations.” (Richards & Rodgers, 2014) To enhance speaking skills among non-linguistic students, digital technologies can be employed in the following ways: through professional simulations (e.g., playing the role of a hotel receptionist in a virtual environment); via idea- and opinion-driven presentations; through interactive dialogue tasks (e.g., conversations with AI bots, speak-to-learn applications). Digital platforms aimed at improving oral skills help learners acquire the following competencies: communicative—speaking accurately, fluently, and appropriately for the context; technological—using multimedia tools effectively; social—engaging in interpersonal, interactive communication; cultural—understanding the cultural context of the target language.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Every learner has a unique style of language acquisition, interests, prior knowledge, and individual pace of speech development. Digital technologies allow for the creation of personalized and adaptive learning environments tailored to each student's needs. In this approach, the student becomes the central agent of the learning process. Learners set their own goals, determine their learning paths, and progress at their own pace. The teacher assumes the role of a facilitator, guide, and motivator. “In pedagogical approaches, the primary role is shifting from the teacher to the learner – the student becomes the active agent of their own learning process.” (Brown, 2015) Key pedagogical advantages of this approach include: students can learn at their own pace (e.g., rewatching videos, re-recording pronunciation); adaptive platforms like Duolingo or ELSA Speak adjust to the learner’s level; progress and speaking activity are monitored in real time (e.g., via Quizlet or ELSA Speak);

students define personal goals (e.g., “100 new words per week,” or “prepare a 10-minute speech”). In summary, this personalized model fosters student self-regulation, independent decision-making, and intrinsic motivation.

Interactivity is a critical factor in improving speaking skills. The use of digital tools helps create such interactive environments. Language learning is inherently a social activity, and interactive methodologies encourage learners to use the target language as a real tool for communication. Learners express opinions, ask and answer questions, explain concepts, and engage in argumentation. Oral skills thus evolve beyond structured drills to a form of social collaboration, where learners influence, discuss, and make decisions together. Digital applications that foster interactive speaking practice include: Breakout Rooms in Zoom/Teams (enable small-group discussions); Flipgrid (allows students to respond to assignments via video); ChatGPT or AI tools (provide simulated conversation partners). These digital tools offer the following benefits: simulating real-life communicative situations; learning linguistic structures within meaningful contexts; turning learners into active participants. “The more engaged and participative the student is in the lesson, the stronger the language acquisition.” (Warschauer & Kern, 2000)

In non-linguistic environments, applying gamification through digital tools increases student engagement, motivation, creativity, and competitiveness in language learning. Gamified settings encourage students to communicate, compete, and compare progress. “Game elements are highly effective pedagogical tools for stimulating learner interaction.” (Beatty, 2013) Examples of gamified language-learning applications include: vocabulary-enhancing games (e.g., Kahoot, Bloocket); apps that award XP points, badges, and achievements; quests and challenge tasks that drive intrinsic motivation. Gamification introduces game-like elements such as points, levels, rewards, and competitive dynamics to boost learner engagement. For non-linguistic learners, gamification provides an enjoyable pathway toward linguistic goals. “Digital gamification fosters safe, motivational environments where students can explore without fear of failure.” (Anderson & West, 2014) Gamified designs with engaging interfaces, reward systems, and low-stress challenge tasks help eliminate boredom, overload, and mental fatigue. “Game-based feedback and reward systems in digital classrooms significantly reduce cognitive and emotional stress.” (Deterding et al., 2011) Gamified team activities and leaderboards also enhance social cohesion, reducing anxiety and isolation. “Collaborative gamified activities on digital platforms foster a sense of connection, value, and peer support among learners.” (Hamari, Koivisto, & Sarsa, 2014)

CONCLUSION

Reflection refers to self-awareness in learning – the process of analyzing, correcting, and assessing one’s language performance. It fosters students’ ability to become self-directed and critical thinkers. Through this reflective approach, learners not only acquire knowledge but also evaluate and improve their skills. Digital tools support this process by enabling: The creation of personalized study schedules and daily reflection journals; Recording and reviewing one’s own speech (e.g., via Flipgrid); Self-assessment and progress tracking (e.g., through Google Classroom feedback). As Chappelle (2001) noted, “Digital technologies transform the learner from a passive recipient into an active author.”

In conclusion, the integration of digital tools into English language learning is rooted in the aforementioned pedagogical theories. These theories play a vital role in shaping effective educational methodologies and strategies, while also fostering learner interest, motivation, and active engagement. Therefore, in the continued development of language learning applications and platforms, it is essential to prioritize not only technological functionality but also sound pedagogical foundations.

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